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Ki-67 proliferation index and expression of vimentin in three different continuous cell lines

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Ki-67 is a nuclear protein which is necessary for cell cycle proliferation, while vimentin is often used as a marker of mesenchymally-derived cells^{1,2}. Expression of these markers can contribute to better interpretation of tumour cell proliferation and cytoarchitecture during both normal development and metastatic progression. The objective was to Determine Ki-67 proliferation index and vimentin expression by means of indirect immunofluorescence in BHK-21/C13, MCF-7 and MRC-5 continuous cell lines. The research was conducted on continuous cell lines BHK-21/C13, MCF-7 and MRC-5. The cell lines were held in incubator on 37 °C, in atmosphere with 100% humidity and 5% CO₂ during the 48h. The cells were subjected to immunofluorescence for Ki-67 and vimentin antigen. Afterwards, every cell line was photographed and the photos were processed in *Fiji* software. Ki-67 proliferation index and the immunofluorescence intensity of vimentin antibody have been determined. Positive expression of Ki-67 antigen was noticed in all three cell lines. Proliferation index in BHK-21/C13 was 97.01%; in MCF-7 was 90.43%; in MCR-5 was 90.58%. Vimentin intermediate filament was present in the cytoplasm of all examined cell lines. Highest values of immunofluorescence intensity for vimentin antibody were shown in BHK-21/C13, while the lowest values were shown in MCF-7. Ki-67 antigen represents a good proliferation indicator while vimentin refers well to cytoarchitecture of examined cell lines.

References

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